

will increase with increasing cationic charge and decreasing distance of separation. The observed slope value is higher than those of the transition metal complexes.

Spectrophotometry. Method of isobestic points: McBryde¹¹ investigated the interactions between Fe^{III} ion and 1,2-dihydroxybenzene-3,5-disulphonic acid in aqueous medium by the spectrophotometric technique. Sm^{III}-2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane system was studied in the present investigation spectrophotometrically. Absorption curves at different pH for the solution containing samarium perchlorate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) and the ligand ($20 \times 10^{-3} M$) were constructed (Fig. 2). The absorption curves intersect at one point at 585 nm (isobestic point) indicating the presence of two different complex species (1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes) in the pH range 2.0–6.0.

Fig. 2. Plots of absorption vs wavelength: pH (1) 2.0, (2) 2.5, (3) 3.5, (4) 4.1, (5) 4.6, (6) 5.5 and (7) 6.0; $\mu = 0.1 M$, Sm^{III}-2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzodibenzoylmethane, isobestic point at 585 nm.

The colour of solution was light brown below pH 3.0 and dark brown above 3.0. The change in colour of the solution at different pH values indicates the formation of complexes between Sm^{III} ion and 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane.

Apparent molar volume: Jahagirdar and Pankanti^{1,2} studied the apparent molar volumes and adiabatic compressibility of 1-amino acids in mixed solvents. Apparent molar volumes of 2'-hydroxy-3,4-benzo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethane in different percentage of dioxane-water mixtures have been studied in the present investigation (Table 2). It is observed that the apparent molar volume decreases continuously with increasing percentage of the organic solvent (i.e. decreasing dielectric constant). This may be due to electrostriction which can be related to the number of water molecules (nH) associated with the ligand. The plot between apparent molar volume and mole fraction

of dioxane shows linear relationship. The same linear relationship was also observed by Jahagirdar and Pankanti^{1,2}.

TABLE 2—APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES $\phi(v)$ OF 2'-HYDROXY-3,4-BENZO-4-NITRODIBENZOYL METHANE IN DIFFERENT PERCENTAGE OF DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Dioxane-Water %	d_0 g cm ⁻³	d g cm ⁻³	$\phi(v)^*$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
70	1.0440	1.0426	1701.00
75	1.0424	1.0412	1474.48
80	1.0414	1.0405	1187.82
85	1.0400	1.0395	804.80
90	1.0378	1.0374	710.15

$$*\phi(v) = \frac{1000}{C} - \frac{1}{d_0} \left(\frac{1000d}{C} - M \right)$$

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the help rendered by Principal, Government Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya, Amravati.

References

- M. L. NARWADE, Ph. D. Thesis, Marathwada University, 1974.
- A. D. SHERRY, C. YOSHIDA, E. R. BIRNBAUM and D. W. DARNALL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 95, 3011.
- S. RAMAMOORTHY and P. G. MANNING, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 1977.
- D. W. DARNALL and E. R. BIRNBAUM, *Biochemistry*, 1973, 12, 489.
- F. J. MILLERIO, ALO SHARDO and C. SHIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, 82, 784.
- S. J. SWAMY and P. LINGAIAH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1974, 16, 723.
- L. G. VAN UITERT and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 5887.
- H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2904.
- J. BJERRUM, *Chem. Rev.*, 1950, 46, 881.
- J. C. JONSK and D. G. VERTAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 1306.
- W. A. E. F. MCBRYDE *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, 42, 1917.
- D. V. JAHAGIRDAR and S. U. PANKANTI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 1955.

Solid State Degradation of Carbamide in Presence of Tin Oxides

B. N. PRASAD and S. BHAGAT*

Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

Manuscript received 17 December 1987, revised 6 April 1988, accepted 12 April 1988

IN continuation of our earlier work on solid state decomposition to correlate solid state chemistry and catalysis and to tailor catalysts to meet specific demands^{1,2}, we presently report on the solid state degradation of carbamide in presence of tin oxide samples of different origins.

TABLE 1—KINETIC DATA FOR DEGRADATION OF CARBAMIDE

Decomp. temp. °C	Sample	Sn ^{II} /Sn ^{IV} ratio	Specific rate ($\times 10^{-4}$ s ⁻¹) at			E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	log A
			140°	150°	160°		
Carbamide alone							
600	S ₁	2.275	1.247	2.015	4.660	23.182	12.458
700	S ₂	0.717	5.544	10.075	12.794	14.841	7.986
800	S ₃	2.092	5.408	9.672	13.626	14.981	7.676
960	S ₄	2.092	6.071	10.418	7.418	18.304	9.674
600	S ₅	1.982	5.388	7.585	7.392	11.305	6.048
600	S ₆	3.123	2.926	4.126	4.672	11.767	6.325
700	S ₆	3.103	2.636	10.619	11.405	20.919	11.105
800	S ₇	2.813	1.944	3.838	7.736	—	—
960	S ₈	0.787	1.919	4.310	6.448	22.880	12.160
600	S ₉	0.179	2.899	5.094	7.955	21.572	11.405
700	S ₁₀	0.052	2.302	3.953	6.013	16.996	8.948
800	S ₁₁	0.048	2.083	3.390	5.081	16.016	8.471
960	S ₁₂	0.756	1.757	3.181	4.762	17.472	9.839

Experimental

Commercial sample of carbamide was used. The different samples were prepared from oxalate, sulphate and chloride of tin(II)³. The samples prepared from tin(II) oxalate at 600, 700, 800 and 960° were labelled as S₁, S₂, S₃ and S₄ respectively. Samples from sulphate and chloride of tin(II) prepared at 600, 700, 800 and 960° were marked as S₅, S₆, S₇ and S₈ respectively for those from sulphate, and S₉, S₁₀, S₁₁ and S₁₂ respectively for those from chloride. The amount of Sn^{II} and Sn^{IV} were determined by standard methods⁴.

Decomposition study: The kinetic study of degradation of carbamide without and with the catalysts at 140, 150 and 160° was done using gasometric method. The mixture of carbamide and catalyst (20 : 1) was ground intimately and the mixture (0.3 g) was taken in the reaction vessel dipped in a glycerine-thermostat maintained at the desired temperature. The volume of the ensuing gas was recorded at regular interval of time by noting the difference in the levels of the fluid in the manometer. The static state of the level showed the completion of the reaction. A plot between log (V_∞ - V_t) and time was drawn.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants estimated from the rate curves log (V_∞ - V_t) vs time, energy of activation and frequency factor calculated from the Arrhenius plot (log K vs 1/T) are recorded in Table 1. It is found that the degradation of carbamide in presence of different oxide samples of tin follows first order kinetics. It is known that the degradation of carbamide at low temperature consists of two steps leading to the formation of degraded products of biuret and ammonia⁵,

The above scheme is found valid for our experiments also.

Fig. 1 shows the plots of volume of ammonia evolved vs time for the thermal degradation of carbamide without and with the sample (S₆) obtained from tin(II) sulphate. It is obvious that all the samples activate the degradation of carbamide although their degree of activation differs. From Fig. 1 it is calculated that without oxide the degradation of carbamide yields 1.35, 2.49 and

Fig. 1. Kinetics of degradation of carbamide: (1), (2), (3) urea, and (4), (5), (6) for (urea + S₆) at 140, 150 and 160°, respectively.

5.95 cm³ of NH₃ at 140, 150 and 160° respectively in 10 min, whereas in presence of sample (S₆), 2.95, 4.58 and 7.9 cm³ of NH₃ are evolved at the corresponding temperatures in the same time and from the same amount of carbamide. Hence we find that the degrees of destabilisation of carbamide are 117.03, 83.93 and 32.77% at 140, 150 and 160° respectively. The result is self-indicative that our samples activate the degradation process. This observation is also confirmed by the data on rate constants (Table 1). The rate constants for the degradation of carbamide in presence of samples are of higher magnitude than that obtained in absence of these samples. Thus tin oxides activate the degradation. Further, the effect of temperature on the rate constant is in accordance with the Arrhenius equation.

